

The HIPPARCOS Reference System

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Abstract

In this talk I will review the system of positions and proper motions such as it may be derived solely from observations with the HIPPARCOS satellite, and dwell especially on its systematic qualities.

The HIPPARCOS reference system will be defined by a catalogue of positions and proper motions for some 100,000 stars brighter than $B = 13$, nominally referred to the equator and equinox of J2000. The average positional mean error at mean epoch ($t_0 \approx 1988.5$) is 1.5 mas (milliarcsec) and the average proper motion mean error about 2.0 mas/yr. The precision of a single position depends mainly on the magnitude (Fig. 1), ecliptical latitude (Fig. 2), and time difference from the mean epoch (Fig. 3).

The most important quality of this system is the very high internal consistency on a global scale. Thus, the true angle between any two catalogue stars can be computed to mas accuracy (near t_0). On the other hand, because it is entirely decoupled from the Earth's rotation, it cannot easily be related with similar accuracy to a dynamically defined equatorial system. The orientation with respect to an ideal (α, δ) -frame is expressed, at a given time, by three small angles ϕ, θ, ψ (Fig. 4), which are thus practically unknown. Because of the uniform proper motions imposed by the reduction model they are however known to be linear functions of time: $\phi(t) = \phi_0 + (t-t_0)\dot{\phi}$, etc; so the system is in effect undefined with respect to the six constants $\phi_0, \theta_0, \psi_0, \dot{\phi}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\psi}$. The last three give the inertial rotation of the system and can be obtained from apparent proper motions of extragalactic objects. The others define the equator (ϕ_0, θ_0) and equinox (ψ_0) and can be obtained only by making reference to Earth-bound observations, e.g. of absolute declinations by radio interferometry. ψ_0 in addition requires that the ecliptic be found, which may be possible by observing minor planets with the satellite.

These orientation and rotation errors do not affect the angles between the stars, i.e. the internal consistency of the system. Systematic errors which do cause errors in the computed angles may be called *system distortions*. One form of very local distortion is due simply to the positive statistical correlation between catalogue data for stars within a few degrees on the sky. As a consequence, the average position or proper motion of N neighbouring stars will not improve as $N^{-1/2}$ but considerably slower (Fig. 5).

Global system distortion may arise from thermal effects on the instrument, such as a periodic variation of the basic angle (γ , an instrument 'constant') with the solar azimuth angle ω (Fig. 6). If $\Delta\gamma = b_1 \sin\omega$, say, then the resulting system of ecliptical longitudes will be twisted roughly an angle $\pm b_1$, as shown in Fig. 7; a variation by $b_4 \sin(4\omega)$ will on the other hand distort the proper motions in longitude as in Fig. 8. These are only two particularly nasty examples of what could happen: most Fourier components give much smaller distortion. However, since uncalibrated variations of γ by a few tenths of a mas must be expected, it seems likely that the HIPPARCOS reference system will suffer from some global distortion on a similar level.

Figure 1

PRECISION VERSUS ECLIPTICAL LATITUDE

$ \beta $	$\epsilon_{\lambda} \cos \beta$	ϵ_{β}	error ellipse
90°	1.4 mas	1.4 mas	
70	1.3	1.4	
50	1.0	1.2	
30	1.8	1.3	
10	2.2	1.4	

Figure 2

PRECISION VERSUS TIME

$\epsilon_{p.m.} = 1.4 \epsilon_{pos}(t_0), \quad t_0 = 1988.5$

$\epsilon_{pos}(t_0 \pm \tau) = \sqrt{1 + 2\tau^2} \epsilon_{pos}(t_0)$

τ	$\sqrt{1 + 2\tau^2}$	$\epsilon_{pos}(t_0 \pm \tau)$
0 yr	1.0	0.0015 as
0.5	1.2	0.0018
1.25	2	0.003
50	70	0.1

Figure 3

SYSTEM ORIENTATION

$\Delta \alpha \cos \delta = -\psi \sin \delta \cos \alpha - \theta \sin \delta \sin \alpha + \psi \cos \delta$

$\Delta \delta = \psi \sin \alpha - \theta \cos \alpha$

$|\psi|, |\theta|, |\phi| < 1 \text{ as}$

$\psi(t) = \psi_0 + (t - t_0) \dot{\psi}$ etc.

ψ_0, θ_0, ϕ_0 = orientation errors at mean epoch t_0

$\dot{\psi}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\phi}$ = system rotation

Figure 4

IMPROVEMENT BY AVERAGING N STARS

Figure 5

Figure 6

DISTORTION OF $\Delta\lambda\cos\beta$ FROM $\Delta\gamma = \sin\omega$ mas

Figure 7.

DISTORTION OF $\mu\lambda\cos\beta$ FROM $\Delta\gamma = \sin 4\omega$ mas

Figure 8.